

tunES

Project acronym: tunES

Grant Agreement Number: 101120926

Project full title: Tuning EPC and SRI instruments to deliver full potential
LIFE Project Grants - Programme for Environment and Climate Action (LIFE)

Call identifier: LIFE-2022-CET-BUILDPERFORM

D3.3 REPORT ON EX-ANTE TESTING AND POLICY OPTIONS

Version: 3.0

Status: Final

Dissemination Level: Public

Submission Date: 27.03.26

Work Package: WP3

Lead partner for this deliverable: AEA

Authors:

Manuela Chriti (AEA)

Georg Vogt (EMP)

Tatiana Novikova (EMP)

Rune Korsholm Andersen
(DTU)

Abstract: This deliverable presents the methodology for developing Policy Options to improve the effectiveness of EPC and SRI across participating Member States in alignment with the European Commission's Better Regulation Guidelines. It includes a list of policy measures organised by thematic pillars, analysis of baselines and Policy Options shaped by Energy Agencies, and Theory of Change.

REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Changes	Reviewer / contributor
0.1	15.01.25	First draft	Tatiana Novikova (EMP)
0.2	29.01.25	Review and comments	Manuela Chriti (AEA)
0.3	19.02.25	Additions after the Consortium meeting	Manuela Chriti (AEA)
0.4	25.02.25	Review and comments	Tatiana Novikova (EMP)
0.5	05.03.25	Additions	Tatiana Novikova (EMP)
0.6	17.02.25	Peer Review	Rune Korsholm Andersen (DTU)
0.7	19.02.25	Final Review	Manuela Chriti (AEA)
1.0	24.03.25	Submission	Georg Vogt (EMP)
1.1	10.02.26	Review and additions based on the PO revision request	Tatiana Novikova (EMP)
2.0	20.02.26	Submission	Georg Vogt (EMP)
2.1	16.03.26	Review and additions based on the PO revision request	Tatiana Novikova (EMP)
3.0	27.03.26	Submission	Georg Vogt (EMP)

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BEM	Building Energy Modelling
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BRG	Better Regulation Guidelines
BRP	Building Renovation Passport
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
EU	European Union
IoT	Internet of Things
MECE	Mutually Exclusive, Collectively Exhaustive
MS	Member State
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan
nZEB	Nearly Zero-energy Building
PO	Policy Option
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
TST	Technical Support Team

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable outlines the **approach, set of policy measures** developed to identify and address challenges related to Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) and Smart Readiness Indicators (SRIs) in the countries participating in the tunES project, **and Policy Options** shaped by Energy Agencies.

The deliverable presents a structured, iterative **approach** for developing Policy Options (POs) following the European Commission's Better Regulation Guidelines (BRG) representative of the current state of work – further steps will be added on the next iteration. The analysis is based on the core steps of the BRG, namely problem analysis, objectives and a broad baseline description. Energy Agencies worked collaboratively to identify the key drivers behind these problems and to set measurable objectives for improving the EPC framework.

In this context, the **baseline** scenario constitutes a key analytical element, representing the current state of EPC and SRI frameworks and projecting their future development in the absence of new policy interventions. As transposition of earlier EPBD iterations differed across Member States it results in varying legislative baselines, i.e. the existing constellation of policy measures is not the same across Member States. As a principle, the study does not conduct comparison of starting points across Member States (i.e. which one was more ambitious in the past) and rather focused on a critical assessment of the baseline and why the problems arise from it to design policy options able to address the underlying drivers.

The development of the **initial set of policy measures** was conducted in multiple stages. Firstly, the project adopted a collaborative whiteboard approach, allowing Energy Agencies to visually map out potential measures, share feedback, and refine ideas in real time. This method provided a flexible and interactive platform for engaging all partners in the process. Building on this foundation, the project transitioned to a structured Excel-based framework, which allows for finer detail being recorded across and within Member States, alignment with EU legislation, and preparation for the impact assessment phase. Where applicable policy measures – independent of the source – are linked to the relevant articles of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD).

Currently, the Energy Agencies are shaping their **Policy Options**. Aside of identifying the baseline and rejected measures, they create at least one Basic, one Advanced, and one Comprehensive Policy Option. As a continuous process, Energy Agencies are preparing internal Policy Papers for discussion with the responsible national ministries and for stakeholder consultations.

Across the seven Member States, 33% of policy measures had already been implemented in the baseline with especially high percentage of implementation in such pillars as EPC scope, EPC triggers, EPC method, and experts. The preferred options are expected to add 58% resulting in an expected coverage of 91% of all measures. This figure is only slightly below the considered maximum of 96%, i.e. even in Member States where no comprehensive option has been selected, most measures are to be added.

The tunES set of policy measures is published on our website and shared with the Next Gen EPC cluster. As part of the sharing process, we hope to gather input from researchers on the theory of change for each measure, with a view to improving the calculations in the impact assessment.

1 Introduction

The tunES project aims to optimise the implementation of EPCs and SRIs to enhance energy efficiency while minimising administrative burdens and transaction costs. This deliverable outlines the project's structured methodology, guided by the BRG Guidelines and Toolbox, for identifying key challenges, setting objectives, establishing baseline scenarios, and developing targeted policy measures to address them.

Using the BRG principles, the project undertook an in-depth analysis of the current situation to identify the main obstacles to effective EPC and SRI implementation. This analysis included the use of tools such as Problem and Objective Trees, which helped define the underlying issues, their drivers, and the goals for improvement. The resulting objectives were formulated to align with both EU and national energy efficiency goals, ensuring that the proposed measures have clear and measurable outcomes. Based on that, Energy Agencies constructed Policy Options in three levels of ambition.

This deliverable, therefore, provides a comprehensive framework for the development of policy measures that support energy agencies in developing solutions suited to their national contexts.

2 Ex-ante testing

The ex-ante testing was planned for the implementation of the SRI in Austria. The results of the national test phase and other associated national projects were to be examined for feasibility and the changes to national legislation and national standards that would be required were to be worked out. Due to the new timetable as defined by the EPBD recast, the calculation method and further details are not clear from today's perspective and will only become clear from a report (report on the testing and implementation of the smart readiness indicator, based on the available results of the national test phases and other relevant projects) in 2026 or the implementing act based on this (detailing the technical modalities for the effective implementation of the scheme including a timeline for a non-committal test-phase at national level, and clarifying the complementary relation of the scheme to the energy performance certificates referred to in Article 16) in 2027. Subcontracting is therefore not anymore considered necessary.

3 Identified problems and objectives

Defining problems and objectives plays a crucial role in the development of Policy Options. The project utilises a Problem and Objective Tree approach, developed from the BRG Toolbox Tool #13: "How to Analyse Problems" and Tool #15: "How to Set Objectives". These tools provide structured guidance for systematically identifying and organising the relationships between the problems, their drivers, and the desired outcomes (objectives). This method not only clarifies the issues but also lays the foundation for formulating coherent and effective Policy Options.

3.1 Methodology

Problem tree

The Problem Tree visually maps out the main problem, its causes (drivers), and its consequences, following the approach outlined in Better Regulation Toolbox Tool #13. This tool helps understand the scope of the problem by ensuring that potential causes and effects are considered in the policy-making process.

Figure 1. Problem Tree

Components of the Problem Tree include:

- **Problem:** The central issue that needs to be addressed, an existing negative situation.
- **Drivers:** Factors leading to the main problem.
- **Consequences:** The effects or impacts of the main problem on various stakeholders.

Each Energy Agency filled out its Problem Tree as the first step in a series of analytical approaches to resolve policy issues in their respective countries. The problem identification process followed Tool #13, where agencies described the current situation and key challenges affecting EPC implementation. They also estimated the magnitude of these issues based on regional statistics.

The identification of the drivers was essential, as the policy measures aim to address them, which will ultimately affect the problem and its consequences. The agencies followed the guidance of Tool #13 by examining regulatory inconsistencies, technological limitations, and varying levels of stakeholder awareness, as well as external factors such as economic trends and technological advancements, which could influence the problem's development.

Objective Tree

The Objective Tree converts the identified problems and their drivers into specific and measurable goals, following the principles of Better Regulation Toolbox Tool #15: “How to Set Objectives”. The objectives are derived directly from the problem analysis and are classified into general objectives (aligned with broader EU goals) and specific objectives (addressing the key drivers of the identified problems).

Figure 2. Objective Tree

The use of Tool #15 ensures that these objectives are precise, measurable, and time-bound, following the S.M.A.R.T. criteria:

- Specific - clearly defined
- Measurable – able to be quantified to measure progress
- Achievable - realistic and properly justified
- Relevant - linked directly to the Drivers identified in the Problem Tree
- Time-Bound - objectives within a specific timeframe to measure progress.

3.2 Overview of problems, drivers, and consequences across the participating Member States

Across seven tunES Member States, the EPC system is facing a number of challenges that affect its effectiveness in promoting energy efficiency and reducing carbon emissions. Despite the strategic importance of EPCs within broader EU energy and climate policies, several common issues have emerged related to the quality of EPCs, the competence of assessors, and the limited action taken on EPC recommendations.

Common Problems Across Member States

- **Low Quality of EPC Data:** EPCs often lack accuracy and completeness, leading to a gap between the calculated energy performance of buildings and their actual consumption. This undermines trust in the certificates, both among building owners and policymakers.
- **Difficulty Understanding EPCs:** End-users often find EPCs difficult to understand, especially when recommendations are not clearly explained or tailored to specific buildings. As a result, the uptake of recommended renovation measures is limited.
- **Incomplete and Inconsistent National EPC Databases:** Many national databases contain fragmented or incomplete data, reducing the usefulness of EPCs for large-scale energy planning and policy making.
- **Insufficient Use of Operational Data:** In many cases, EPCs rely on theoretical models rather than actual operational energy consumption data, creating discrepancies between predicted and real performance.

Key Drivers of Problems

- **Lack of Mandatory Training for EPC Assessors:** Many EPC assessors across Member States lack mandatory training or certification, which leads to inconsistencies in the quality of EPCs. In some cases, no mandatory retraining is required, further exacerbating these issues as methodologies evolve.
- **Limited Validation and Oversight:** National or regional authorities often do not validate EPCs rigorously, allowing low-quality certificates to be issued without proper oversight.
- **Lack of Tailored Recommendations in EPCs:** EPCs often do not include specific recommendations for improving building energy performance, or they are presented in a way that is difficult for building owners or tenants to understand and act upon.
- **Financial Barriers:** The rising cost of issuing EPCs, along with limited financial incentives to upgrade buildings based on EPC recommendations, further hinders the effective use of these certificates to drive energy efficiency.
- **Technical Gaps and Interoperability Issues:** In many tunES Member States, the technical systems used to manage EPC data are not interoperable, which limits the ability to integrate EPC data into national energy planning and market-driven energy efficiency programmes.

Consequences

- **Discrepancy Between EPC Ratings and Actual Performance:** Widespread reliance on theoretical models rather than actual consumption data leads to discrepancies between EPC ratings and actual building performance, undermining trust in EPCs as a reliable tool.
- **Limited Renovation Uptake:** Due to low confidence in the quality and relevance of EPCs, building owners and tenants are less likely to invest in energy renovations based on the certificates' recommendations. This impedes progress towards EU energy efficiency and climate goals.
- **Underutilisation of EPC Data in Policy Planning:** The incomplete or inaccurate nature of many national EPC databases means that EPC data are often not utilised effectively for national, regional, or local energy planning. This limits the potential of EPCs to inform strategic decisions on building renovation and energy efficiency measures.
- **Lack of Engagement with Energy Renovation Programmes:** Without clear, actionable recommendations and reliable data, there is limited engagement from building owners in energy renovation programmes aimed at achieving near-zero energy building (nZEB) standards.

External Factors Influencing EPC Effectiveness

- **EU and National Energy Policies:** The ambitious targets set by EU policies such as the Green Deal, the EPBD, and the Renovation Wave rely heavily on the effective implementation of EPCs.
- **Climate Change and Energy Crisis:** The increasing urgency to mitigate climate change, combined with the volatility of energy prices, places additional pressure on Member States to use EPCs as tools to reduce energy consumption in buildings.

3.3 Overview of objectives across the participating Member States

To address the common problems associated with EPCs and enhance their role in promoting energy efficiency across the EU, Energy Agencies are pursuing several key objectives. These objectives focus on improving the quality and reliability of EPCs, increasing public engagement and trust, and fostering energy efficiency through actionable recommendations and data management.

Improving EPC assessor competence and training

A recurring objective across Member States is the need to establish or enhance mandatory training programmes for EPC assessors. This includes providing initial training followed by periodic updates or recertifications to ensure that assessors remain competent and up to date with evolving technologies, methodologies, and tools, such as the SRI and BRPs.

- **Problem Addressed:** Low competence and inconsistency among EPC assessors, leading to poor-quality certificates.
- **Outcome:** More competent and qualified assessors, resulting in improved accuracy and reliability of EPC data. This will also increase trust in EPCs and encourage building owners to implement energy saving measures based on EPC recommendations.

Enhancing EPC data quality and validation mechanisms

Member States are implementing objectives to improve the quality and reliability of EPC data. This includes the introduction of national systems for EPC quality control, with mandatory checks before data is entered into local or national databases. Additionally, automated

monitoring and inspection systems are being developed to ensure compliance with established standards.

- **Problem Addressed:** Inconsistent and inaccurate EPC data due to poor validation and oversight.
- **Outcome:** Accurate, high-quality EPCs that reflect the actual building energy performance, improving their relevance for energy planning and policymaking. This will also mitigate the risk of fraud and enhance the overall integrity of national EPC systems.

Revising EPC templates and improving user-friendliness

Another key objective is to make EPCs more user-friendly by redesigning their layout to include clearer information on energy classes, tailored recommendations, potential financial savings, and descriptions of energy efficiency measures. The goal is to make EPCs easier for building owners and tenants to understand, thereby increasing the likelihood of action being taken based on EPC data.

- **Problem Addressed:** Difficulty in understanding EPC data and recommendations, leading to low end-user engagement.
- **Outcome:** Clearer, more accessible EPCs that empower building owners to make informed decisions about energy renovations. This will also improve public trust and acceptance of EPCs, contributing to increased energy efficiency measures.

Leveraging operational consumption data for accuracy

Many Member States are focusing on incorporating operational energy consumption data into EPCs, moving away from theoretical models that do not accurately reflect real-world energy performance. The use of actual consumption data is critical for making EPCs a more reliable tool for assessing building energy efficiency.

- **Problem Addressed:** Discrepancy between calculated EPC ratings and actual energy consumption, reducing EPC relevance.
- **Outcome:** EPCs that provide a more accurate reflection of building energy performance, enhancing their utility for energy planning and supporting the achievement of national energy efficiency goals.

Developing tailored energy efficiency recommendations

Member States aim to improve the effectiveness of EPCs by developing tailored recommendations that are specific to each building's unique characteristics. Instead of generic energy-saving advice, EPCs will provide actionable and customised guidance on how to improve energy performance, including staged renovation measures and funding opportunities.

- **Problem Addressed:** Generic or unclear EPC recommendations that are difficult for building owners to act on.
- **Outcome:** More relevant and actionable energy efficiency recommendations, leading to greater adoption of energy-saving renovations and contributing to long-term energy and climate goals.

Reconstructing national EPC databases

Another important objective is the reconstruction of national EPC databases to ensure that they are comprehensive, up-to-date, and accessible. This includes improving the user

interface, adding more detailed data from EPCs, and introducing feedback mechanisms and control systems to verify the accuracy of the information stored in these databases.

- **Problem Addressed:** Incomplete or low-quality EPC databases that undermine the reliability and usefulness of EPC data.
- **Outcome:** Improved databases that provide reliable, accurate, and comprehensive EPC data, which can be effectively used for national, regional, and local energy planning and policy development.

Public engagement and awareness campaigns

Member States recognise the importance of increasing public awareness of the value and importance of EPCs. Objectives include launching media awareness campaigns, developing interactive digital platforms, and conducting information campaigns to educate building owners and tenants on how to use EPC data to improve building energy performance.

- **Problem Addressed:** Low awareness and engagement with EPCs among building owners and the general public.
- **Outcome:** Increased public awareness and understanding of EPCs, leading to higher adoption of energy efficiency measures and greater interest in upgrading buildings to nearly zero-energy building (nZEB) standards.

Providing Financial Incentives and Support

Several Member States are introducing objectives to offer financial incentives and support the adoption of advanced tools like Building Energy Modelling (BEM) and Building Information Modelling (BIM). These tools can enhance the accuracy and effectiveness of EPCs, but financial barriers often prevent their widespread use.

- **Problem Addressed:** Financial and technical barriers that limit the use of advanced energy efficiency tools.
- **Outcome:** Greater use of advanced tools in energy performance assessments, leading to more accurate EPCs and better energy planning across Member States. Financial support will also encourage building owners to adopt energy efficiency measures.

4 Development of Policy Options

The development of Policy Options in the tunES project follows a structured, iterative process guided by the principles outlined in the European Commission's BRG. The aim is to identify, refine, and evaluate realistic Policy Options that address the identified problems and objectives in energy performance and related areas. This process involves building a strong foundation, exploring a wide range of alternatives, and narrowing down to the most viable and effective solutions.

4.1 Collection of policy measures

As the first step, policy measures were collected based on the consultations with stakeholder groups, existing policies, best practices, the renewed EPBD. The collection of policy measures within the tunES project follows a structured, iterative process guided by the European Commission's Better Regulation Guidelines (BRG). The goal is to gather and refine a comprehensive range of measures that address specific problems and objectives related to EPCs and SRIs, creating a foundation for the eventual development of Policy Options. This process includes establishing a strong baseline, exploring a variety of possible measures, and identifying those that are most feasible and effective.

4.2 Methodology

The tunES project adopts a methodology that aligns with the BRG, particularly focusing on Better Regulation Toolbox Tool #16 “How to Identify Policy Options”, and conducted the following steps:

1. **Compiling Policy Measures:** Considering a wide range of policy measures, from less intrusive to the more interventionist for consequent Policy Option development. Collecting policy measures in tunES was performed in two steps:
 - a. **Creative Stage:** Collaborative effort using a digital whiteboard to brainstorm and visually organise a wide array of potential policy measures. The approach allowed Energy Agencies to discuss, adapt, and categorise measures by ambition level (basic, advanced, comprehensive) and discard those not suited to their national contexts.
 - b. **Structured Tool:** Following the creative stage, the process transitioned to a more organised Excel-based methodology. This structured tool mapped each policy measure to the relevant EPBD articles, ensuring alignment with EU regulations.
2. **Constructing a Baseline:** Establishing a ‘no-policy-change’ scenario that includes all relevant EU and national policies expected to remain in force.
3. **Constructing Policy Options:** Identification of the most viable options, describing in detail the key aspects of the retained policy options allowing an in-depth analysis of the associated impacts.
4. **Theory of Change:** Description of the mechanism by which the baseline is affected through policy options (and measures within) to achieve the objectives set for the policy initiative.

This structured process ensures that the identified policy measures are effective, efficient, and coherent, addressing the core problems related to EPCs and SRIs. By systematically compiling a comprehensive set of measures, this approach provides a solid foundation for developing Policy Options—combinations or packages of measures tailored to address the identified problems in their entirety.

4.3 Compiling policy measures – creative stage

Building on the structured framework, the TST initially implemented the whiteboard approach, which was carried out using Microsoft Teams’ Whiteboard tool. This method was introduced as a collaborative, visual tool to help identify, organise, and refine policy measures. The digital whiteboard allowed Energy Agencies to interact in real-time, visually mapping out policy measures structured by:

- **tunES building blocks:** Understanding EPC, Upgrading EPC, Databases and Tools, Integration of Instruments, SRI Development and Deployment.
- **Pillars:** Main thematic areas or strategic priorities that structure the policy framework.

At first, all partners worked together on a main whiteboard (Figure 3) to collaboratively review and improve the initial set of policy measures. This process involved gathering feedback, refining measures, and ensuring clarity across all policy components. This collaborative phase helped to establish a shared understanding of the policy measures and provided a platform for all partners to contribute their expertise.

Figure 3. Results of the Main Whiteboard

After this initial collaborative review, the whiteboard was copied for each tunES country, where Energy Agencies then worked independently. In this phase, each country customised its whiteboard by colour-coding the policy measures according to their perceived level of ambition—basic (green), advanced (yellow), or comprehensive (red). Additionally, they could choose to discard measures they considered irrelevant or already in place within their national context (baseline measures). This flexible, visual approach allowed each country to tailor the policy measures to their specific needs while providing opportunities for dialogue, refinement, and clarification.

The whiteboard approach had successfully fostered initial collaboration and helped shape the development of Policy Options. Following the feedback from partners during the consortium meeting in Rome in September 2024, it was decided to further refine and enhance the process by adopting a more structured framework, leading to the transition to the Excel-based approach, which ensured greater precision and alignment with the project’s objectives.

4.4 Compiling policy measures – structured tool

Following the valuable insights gained from the collaborative work on the whiteboard and the discussions during the consortium meeting in Rome, the team wished to induce further analysis and easing comparability in the coming stages. The transition to the Excel-based methodology was driven by four key factors:

- **Country-specific variations:** It became evident that the baselines across tunes Member States differ and should be recorded accordingly.
- **Alignment with the EPBD:** The status of the EPBD keeps evolving with further documentation and guidance to follow. To prepare, clear referencing and clear IDs are required which can be traced to the EPBD and Member States in order to ensure a consistent impact assessment.
- **Efficiency and Impact Assessment:** In light of the evolving guidance, a matrix structure simplified a MECE-compliant structure (i.e. exclusive and collectively exhaustive). During the process the team further realised that it provided an opportunity to improve the collection of theory of change
- **Replicability:** The team believes that this structure is easier to replicate saving effort and improving communication with other energy agencies.

Each policy measure was mapped directly to the relevant EPBD articles, guaranteeing full alignment with EU regulations. This mapping allowed for a more efficient and focused approach, ensuring that the policy measures were both comprehensive and legally grounded.

4.4.1 Excel Tool overview

Figure 4 presents the Excel Tool which was designed by TST. The image was divided into two parts for better readability of the informative and interactive components. The Tool combines the collection of policy measures and policy options design process. The informative part is the collection of policy measures providing detailed information about the measures with reference to tunES building blocks and EPBD articles which can be filtered to focus on specific areas or EPBD articles. The interactive part for policy option design enables the user to determine which measures are already part of a baseline and select measures as part of one or several policy options at different levels of ambition.

Figure 4. The Excel Tool overview (divided into 2 parts – measures and policy options)

Ur	U	D	Ir	Sf	ID	Pillar	Measure	EPBD
	x				A01	EPC Scope	Certification is required for the entire non-residential building	-
	x				A02	EPC Scope	Certification is required for each individual non-residential building unit	-
	x				A03	EPC Scope	Certification is required for the entire residential building	-
	x				A04	EPC Scope	Certification is required for each individual residential building unit	-
	x				A05	EPC Scope	Certification of building units may be based on the whole building	19(11)a - o
	x				A06	EPC Scope	Certification of building units may be based on the assessment of another representative building unit	19(11)b - o

Baseline	Basic	Advanced		Comprehensive		Reject	Used
	P01	P02.1	P02.2	P03.1	P03.2		
							0
							0
							0
							0
							0
							0

The key elements of the Excel Tool are:

- **Original building blocks** (Understanding EPC, Upgrading EPC, Databases and Tools, Integration of Instruments, SRI): These columns track each measure to the tunES building blocks. TST distributed measures at the tool design stage.
- **ID:** This column displays the unique code assigned to each measure, helping to verify if Energy Agencies have added any new measures. TST inserted the IDs at the tool design stage.
- **Pillar (detail below):** This column represents thematic categories that address critical areas requiring attention helping to organise policy measures in a structured way. TST divided the measures into pillars at the tool design stage.
- **Measure:** The core element of the table, this column lists the specific action or interventions proposed under each pillar. Measures were collected in a collaborative work with TST identifying them from EPBD and Good Practice Collection and Energy Agencies enriching the list based on their experience and needs.
- **EPBD Mapping:** Where applicable, policy measures are mapped to the relevant EPBD articles (shown in the EPBD column), ensuring full compliance with EU regulations and helping distinguish between mandatory and optional measures. The original text is available as comment. TST included the reference to the specific articles at the tool design stage.

- **Baseline, Basic, Advanced, Comprehensive:** These columns classify the level of ambition of each policy measure. Energy Agencies can easily assign measures to different levels of ambition, with Basic representing the most straightforward and cost-effective interventions, and Comprehensive representing the highest ambition and most impactful measures. The distribution of the measures into the policy options was done by Energy Agencies with the support of TST based on the analysis of problem and current situation as well as set objectives for each MS.
- **Reject:** This column allows Energy Agencies to mark which measures they intend to discard. Energy Agencies decide to mark a measure as rejected based on their baseline and national context.
- **Used:** This column uses a formula to automatically count how many times a measure is being considered in different Policy Options.
- **Theory of Change:** This column was planned for providing an explanation of how the measure contributes to achieving the desired outcomes. It will be developed at further steps.
- **Comments and Notes:** The Notes column allows for additional feedback and clarifications. Energy Agencies can leave comments, add suggestions, or highlight potential challenges directly within the table. This enhances collaboration and keeps the discussion transparent and focused.

4.4.2 Pillars for policy measures

All policy measures collected by tunES are grouped by thematic pillars. These measures address key areas of EPCs and SRIs, supporting the alignment of Member States' approaches with national and EU-wide energy efficiency and climate goals.

The policy measures serve as the foundation from which Energy Agencies are shaping their Policy Options. Organised by thematic pillars, they represent a broad framework that ensures comprehensive coverage of key areas in EPC and SRI development. This iterative process will continue to refine and finalise the Policy Options in alignment with national and EU-wide energy goals, providing a robust platform for future implementation. The table below presents the pillars and their explanations:

Table 1. Pillars And Their Definitions

Pillar	Explanation
EPC Scope	Focuses on the applicability and requirements for certification across different building types.
EPC Triggers	Defines the events that mandate the issuance of an EPC.
EPC Method	Sets the framework for national methodology to calculate EPCs, including allowed methods, data requirements etc.
Uptake	Covers actions designed to increase acceptance of EPCs and understanding of issued EPCs.
Uptake-SRI	Covers actions designed to increase acceptance of SRIs and understanding of issued SRIs.
EPC Renewal	Describes how EPCs may or can be updated with particular focus on avoiding unbeneficial administrative burden.

EPC Display	Specifies how and when the EPC should be shown or provided.
Experts	Lists professional requirements and public data on EPC and SRI experts.
Enforcement	Guides how quality of EPCs is to be ensured.
EPC Design	Describes requirements on the design and presentation of the EPC.
EPC Front Page	Describes the content to be displayed on the first page of the EPC.
EPC Content	Lists other required or optional content for the EPC.
EPC Content – Recommendations	Guides how recommendations are to be provided on EPCs.
Database	Describes the framework and lists requirements for national database(s) for EPC and SRI.
Database – Access	Lists the requirements for accessibility and transparency of EPC data.
Integration (NON-EPBD)	List further options beyond EPBD on integration of EPC, SRI, BRP. – Wherever possible such findings
BRP	Refers to the issuance and content of renovation passports
BRP Content	Lists required or optional content for the BRP.
SRI Trigger	Defines the events that mandate the issuance of an EPC.
SRI Method	Sets the framework for national methodology to calculate SRIs, including allowed methods, data requirements etc

4.4.3 List of policy measures

Policy measures - independent of the source - have been tracked to the EPBD. Any measure which is not clearly reflected in the EPBD carries as dash in the according column. The full list is presented in ANNEX 1. tunES Policy Measures and Policy Options presents the full list of policy measures.

4.5 Constructing a baseline

Constructing a baseline is an essential step in the Policy Option development process, as outlined in BRG Tool #16. The baseline scenario represents the current state of EPCs and SRIs and projects future developments without any new policy interventions. It serves as a reference point for assessing the impact of proposed Policy Options, making it essential for comparison and decision-making throughout the project.

The baseline scenario is created by following these key steps:

- **Current situation analysis:** A thorough analysis of the current state of EPCs. This includes documenting EPC coverage, accuracy, usage, and the integration of smart technologies. Relevant factors such as energy consumption patterns, carbon emissions, and national policies are also considered.

- **Qualitative assessment of future trends:** Estimating how EPCs will evolve over time without new policies. This includes evaluating the influence of technological advancements, economic conditions, and existing policies. Environmental factors, such as climate change and its potential impact on energy demand, are also assessed.
- **Defining key assumptions:** The baseline's accuracy depends on clearly defined assumptions, including the continuity of existing policies, expected technological advancements, economic trends, and environmental factors like climate change.
- **Developing quantitative projections:** Based on the qualitative assessment and key assumptions, the baseline includes measurable projections of future developments. This covers aspects such as EPC coverage and the projected energy performance of buildings.
- **Validation and adjustments:** To ensure the baseline is realistic, it is validated through stakeholder consultations, expert feedback, and adjustments based on real-world data. This ensures that the baseline remains accurate and provides a solid foundation for comparing policy.

4.5.1 Overview of baselines in participating Member States

The Member States demonstrate a range of current situations, projected evolutions, and underlying assumptions regarding EPCs and SRIs. The baseline assessment reveals both common challenges and opportunities, all of which shape the trajectory of EPC and SRI implementation and future energy efficiency advancements.

In most tunES participating Member States, EPC issuance has been well established, with millions of EPCs issued in recent years. However, there is considerable variation in the quality, accuracy, and purpose of these certificates.

- **EPC scope:** In several Member States, EPC databases are fragmented or incomplete, leading to gaps in data accessibility and accuracy. All seven countries implemented the validity of EPCs not exceeding 10 years for all building types. Broad exemptions apply to specific building categories such as agricultural non-residential buildings, places of worship, temporary buildings, industrial sites, and small standalone buildings under 50 sqm. These exemptions indicate a widely accepted principle that certain building types do not require EPC certification, likely due to their limited energy use or distinct functional characteristics. The requirement that EPCs apply to joint ownership or common property is another widely implemented measure, reinforcing the importance of energy certification in multi-ownership contexts.
- **EPC triggers and methods:** EPCs are required during key transactions such as construction, sale, and rent. Most countries require EPC during major renovations and for public buildings, although the requirement for rental contract renewals is less widespread. Methodologically, EPCs focus on thermal performance, insulation, and renewable energy, though the adoption of advanced concepts like life-cycle assessments and energy performance gaps is limited. For EPC methodologies, all countries incorporate key factors into their assessments, including thermal capacity, insulation, passive heating, cooling systems, thermal bridges, heating and hot water installations, RES capacity and storage, air-conditioning installations, built-in lighting installations, and considerations for building design, orientation, and outdoor climate. Additionally, the inclusion of solar exposure, cogeneration-produced electricity, and district heating and cooling systems as positive influences is a universally established practice. The inclusion of various building types (residential, office, educational, healthcare, hospitality, and commercial buildings) in EPC assessment is also consistently implemented.

- **EPC uptake and display:** Some countries have central EPC websites or have one-stop-shops for related services. However, proactive engagement strategies for building owners such as renovation recommendations for lower-rated buildings are lacking. Transparency extends to transactions, as EPCs are required in some countries to be shown to new tenants or buyers whenever a trigger event occurs. In the public sector, a similar principle applies, with EPCs being made publicly visible in prominent spaces within public buildings, reinforcing the expectation of compliance with energy efficiency standards. These measures collectively indicate that EPC policies function primarily as informational tools, ensuring visibility but not necessarily driving engagement or action.
- **Experts and enforcement:** EPC experts operate independently and are free from conflicts of interest. Similarly, the requirement that EPC experts can be self-employed or employed by either public or private entities is an accepted norm, allowing for flexibility in the profession. Another common baseline measure is transparency in training and certification. Ensuring that information on training and certification is publicly available provides assurance that EPC experts meet standardised qualifications. Enforcement is strong in most countries, requiring inspection reports and independent control systems, although quality checks and delegation of control systems vary. Inspection reports are to be available to authorities upon request, ensuring that assessments can be reviewed for accuracy and accountability. Similarly, a clear definition of EPC validity is in place in most cases, providing consistency in enforcement.
- **EPC design and content:** Digitalisation of EPCs is common in Member States. Most countries display important performance metrics like greenhouse gas emissions and energy use, however the inclusion of additional features such as life-cycle emissions, energy storage, and electric vehicle charging points is rare. This fact illustrates that EPCs serve as foundational tools for energy efficiency but lack comprehensive environmental and technological data. A common national visual identity for EPCs is another standard measure between participating Member States, aiming for consistency and ease of recognition across regulatory frameworks.
- **Databases:** Data management across countries is inconsistent, with some having national EPC databases but limited interoperability with land registries or other building systems. Data access is often restricted, with GDPR-compliant security measures in place, but public access remains limited. These steps ensure that EPC data, particularly personal and building-related information, is handled responsibly and securely.
- **Integration:** No country has marked any policy measures for integrating EPCs with other tools, showing that efforts to enhance energy efficiency through advanced technologies are still in early stages. The lack of baseline adoption highlights that integration with digital building management tools is not yet a regulatory priority in many regions due to the complexity of standardising different systems and databases.
- **BRP:** Policies related to BRP implementation are in the early stages, with only two countries marking some key measures as a baseline, such as financial support for vulnerable households and providing graphical representations of renovation steps. However, no country has yet adopted measures for integrating EPC and BRP or developing tools for updating BRPs.
- **SRI:** SRI is similarly in the early stages of adoption in most Member States. Testing phases and pilot programs are underway, though widespread implementation remains limited. In some cases, the necessary legal frameworks for SRIs are still pending. This indicates that, while the need for smart readiness in large buildings is recognised, most countries are still developing practical implementation mechanisms.

Expected evolution without additional policy interventions

If no further policy measures are implemented, the evolution of the EPC and SRI schemes is expected to remain slow, with several challenges persisting:

- **Limited renovation uptake:** The renovation rate of existing buildings is projected to remain low. Current renovation rates are insufficient to meet ambitious energy and climate goals set for 2030 and 2050. While energy renovation programmes exist, they are often underfunded, and the public lacks sufficient awareness or incentives to initiate large-scale energy efficiency improvements.
- **Stagnation in SRI development:** In the absence of new policy interventions, SRIs will likely see limited progress, as legal and institutional barriers will continue to slow their adoption. Without a clear regulatory push, the inclusion of smart readiness in energy performance assessments will remain minimal.
- **Data fragmentation:** Databases and tools that manage EPC and SRI data are likely to remain fragmented, with incomplete datasets preventing their full potential for integration into national and regional energy planning strategies. This limits the ability of policymakers to leverage EPC and SRI data for large-scale energy efficiency programmes.
- **Economic influence:** The real estate market and economic growth will likely continue to drive EPC issuance in some Member States. However, the focus will remain on transactional purposes rather than improving energy efficiency. This will perpetuate the status quo, with little impetus to upgrade buildings based on EPC recommendations.

Validation and adjustments

Member States plan to adjust their baseline scenarios as more data and stakeholder feedback become available. The current assumptions and projections have been validated through consultations with national Energy Agencies, ministries, and external experts. Several key validation mechanisms have been highlighted:

- **Consultations with experts:** Expert opinions are being sought to refine assumptions about energy performance trends, renovation rates, and technology adoption. These consultations are expected to guide the adjustment of key indicators and assumptions over time.
- **Stakeholder feedback:** Energy Agencies plan to engage with a broad range of stakeholders, including building owners, assessors, and policymakers, to validate baseline data and ensure it accurately reflects real-world conditions.
- **Data integration:** As databases become more interoperable and comprehensive, Member States will refine their projections on EPC issuance, energy performance, and smart readiness. Future adjustments to baseline scenarios will reflect a more accurate and integrated view of national energy performance.

Emerging trends and insights

While the current baseline scenario highlights several challenges, emerging trends across Member States also offer promising insights for the future:

- **Digitalisation of EPC processes:** Member States are increasingly recognising the need to digitise and standardise EPC processes, which will enhance data quality and accuracy, making EPCs more useful for both end-users and policymakers.
- **Smart technologies and energy management:** The integration of smart technologies, such as IoT devices and advanced energy management systems, is expected to grow, driving improvements in both EPC and SRI accuracy. These technologies will also facilitate

better real-time data on energy consumption and performance, leading to more actionable insights.

- **Public incentives:** Several Member States are focusing on public incentive programmes to promote building renovations and energy efficiency. These programs, combined with increasing awareness of climate change, are expected to drive demand for energy-efficient homes and workplaces.

4.6 Designing Policy Options

After the policy measures were collected and grouped according to pillars in the Excel Tool, the TST instructed Energy Agencies on the next steps in the process of development of a range of Policy Options for the targeted strategy.

Using the Excel Tool with identified range of policy measures, Energy Agencies had to define each measure in appropriate columns as one or several Policy Options in three levels of ambition - basic, advanced, comprehensive:

- Basic Policy Option refers to set of measures which is easy to implement, considers minimal costs, and targets specific issues without broader changes.
- Advanced Policy Option requires more detailed planning and coordination, higher but manageable costs, and addresses multiple facets of the problem.
- Comprehensive Policy Option includes in-depth planning and significant stakeholder engagement, requires substantial financial and human resources, addresses all aspects of the problem.

Differentiation of Policy Options into levels of ambition ensures a structured and flexible approach to policymaking as it provides range of choice, facilitates cost-benefit analysis, and increases political administrative feasibility.

Policy Options are based on good practice and national context across the building blocks they are tackling to define and prioritise a set of feasible measures, given technical, institutional, political or cultural parameters. When shaping Policy Options, Energy Agencies considered the information discussed during the stakeholder consultations and meetings with local ministries.

Energy Agencies employed measures from each pillar thus covering all aspects identified in tunES building blocks and constructing Policy Options which present alternatives for the national and European approach to EPC and SRI.

Table 2 presents the statistics on which share of policy measures in each pillar were identified by participating Member States in the Baseline or in Policy Options at different levels of ambition. The shares are averages across MS calculated by counting how often measures were selected. For instance, in the case of “EPC Scope” pillar, there are 16 measures which could be selected by 7 Energy Agencies 112 times as a Baseline measure, as a measure for one or several Policy Options, or as rejected measures. The share 63% means that the measures in the pillar were selected 70 times to show the Baseline, 4% means that they were selected 4 times for PO1, 12% means that they were selected 13 times for PO2, and 13% means that 2 more measures were selected to design PO3.

The column “**Considered**” describes which share of measures would be deployed if the comprehensive option would be selected by each Energy Agencies including already deployed measures in the baseline. The column “**Covered by Preferred POs**” describes the share of measures Energy Agencies selected to deploy in the Policy Option which is a preferred one

based on the conducted Impact Assessment. The column **“To be transposed”** if the preferred option is implemented exactly as described, is the sum of baseline and preferred option.

Averages are provided for each column. Across the seven Member States, 33% of measures had already been implemented in the baseline. The preferred options are expected to add 58% resulting in an expected coverage of 91% of all measures. This figure is only slightly below the considered maximum of 96%, i.e. even in Member States where no comprehensive option has been selected, most measures are being added.

More details on Policy Options considered by Energy Agencies are collected in ANNEX 1. tunES Policy Measures and Policy Options.

Table 2. Distribution of policy measures identified by MS as Baseline and Policy Options

Pillar	No. of measures	Shares as entered				Shares calculated		
		Baseline	PO1 Basic	PO2 Advanced	PO3 Comprehens.	Considered (Baseline + Max PO)	Covered by Preferred POs	To be Transposed (Baseline+ Preferred)
EPC Scope	16	63%	4%	12%	13%	76%	11%	74%
EPC Triggers	8	86%	11%	11%	13%	98%	13%	99%
EPC Method	41	74%	14%	18%	24%	98%	19%	93%
Uptake	8	20%	43%	70%	80%	100%	66%	86%
Uptake-SRI	7	20%	33%	59%	69%	90%	57%	77%
EPC Renewal	3	5%	57%	81%	95%	100%	95%	100%
EPC Display	8	38%	45%	57%	61%	98%	57%	95%
Experts	7	76%	16%	22%	24%	100%	29%	105%
Enforcement	6	64%	12%	31%	33%	98%	31%	95%
EPC Design	5	54%	29%	46%	46%	100%	46%	100%
EPC Front Page	9	52%	38%	44%	48%	100%	48%	100%
EPC Content	39	30%	34%	54%	63%	93%	52%	82%
EPC Content – Recommendations	13	15%	41%	67%	74%	89%	68%	83%
Database	16	26%	38%	57%	74%	100%	71%	97%
Database – Access	12	19%	30%	52%	77%	96%	70%	89%

Integration	6	2%	19%	52%	98%	100%	69%	71%
BRP	13	5%	55%	77%	92%	98%	89%	94%
BRP Content	18	6%	53%	71%	91%	97%	85%	91%
SRI Trigger	2	0%	50%	86%	100%	100%	100%	100%
SRI Method	23	2%	36%	72%	93%	96%	83%	85%
Average		33%	33%	52%	63%	96%	58%	91%

The high numbers of “Considered” column show that the almost all policy measures could be considered for implementation by Energy Agencies if they decide for the Comprehensive PO taking into account number of policy measures already included in the baseline which is especially high in some of the pillars.

From the seven Energy Agencies, three chose a Comprehensive PO, the most ambitious, as a Preferred one, another three decided for an Advanced PO, and only one Agency preferred a Basic PO (the least ambitious). This fact leads to high percentages of policy measures covered by the Preferred POs and consequently to a high number of measures to be transposed combining the baseline and Preferred Options in the seven MS.

The following sections describe the increasing ambition of applying measures in each pillar based on the baseline already deployed.

4.6.1 Overview of Basic Policy Options in participating MS across policy measures

EPC scope: Since the Energy Agencies are implementing most of the measures in this pillar at the baseline level, only few measures are identified by Energy Agencies to be implemented at the basic level of ambition: allowing certification of building units based on the whole building and the introduction of an active opt-out for residential buildings used for less than four months and under 25% occupancy. These measures indicate an inclination towards increased flexibility in certification processes while maintaining regulatory control.

EPC triggers and methods: Energy Agencies include requiring EPCs when rental contracts are renewed, expanding EPC considerations to ventilation and indoor climate conditions, and recognising positive energy performance influences to the basic set of Policy Options. The methodology to take BACS and building capabilities into account and independent EPC experts issuing certificates through virtual means have also been adopted by some countries at this level.

EPC uptake and display: Some countries have defined to implement policies aimed at making EPCs more user-friendly and increasing public engagement at the basic Policy Option level. Providing easy-to-read guidance documents for EPC and BRP represents a step toward simplifying the certification process for non-experts. Similarly, targeted EPC information campaigns via mass and social media indicate a shift toward proactive communication strategies. Institutional support mechanisms also emerge at this level, with one-stop shops planned to be introduced in some countries to assist building owners in understanding and acting upon EPC recommendations.

Experts and enforcement: Some countries included additional measures aimed at improving the regulation and visibility of EPC experts. Public access to expert information is also being strengthened, with some Agencies requiring frequent updates on certified experts to ensure that property owners and buyers have access to up-to-date, credible professionals. In terms

of enforcement, some countries included quality checks on EPCs and establishment of an independent EPC control system to the basic Policy Option

EPC design and content: Energy Agencies decided to implement measures aimed at enhancing EPC readability, accessibility, and the granularity of displayed data at the basic level. This includes efforts to redesign the layout of the first EPC page, making it more visually appealing and summarising key energy performance indicators in clear format. EPCs at this level also incorporate reference values such as nZEB standards. Greater emphasis is given to providing recommendations for energy efficiency improvements, though these remain general rather than building specific.

Databases: Interoperability with other building-related registries is included to the basic Policy Options level with some countries working on integrating EPC data with national building cadastres and land registries. In terms of accessibility, machine-readable EPC data formats are introduced at this level, facilitating automated processing and integration with digital tools. Several Energy Agencies identified the need to provide easy and free access to EPCs for tenants, owners, and experts at basic level, though access remains conditional and limited to certain stakeholders.

Integration: A few countries have identified laying the groundwork for EPC interoperability, mainly focusing on data-sharing frameworks and certification alignment. The most common basic measure involves ensuring that EPC and SRI tools can exchange data, allowing buildings' smart readiness to be evaluated alongside their energy performance.

BRP: Some countries aim to expand BRP functionalities by including additional information, such as estimated cost projections, payback periods, and GHG savings for each step of the renovation process. Policies at this level link BRP with financial incentives, such as subsidies and price regulations, making renovations more affordable and accessible.

SRI implementation: Most Energy Agencies start to incorporate methodologies for calculating the SRI at the basic level, ensuring that the indicator is aligned with energy performance certification frameworks. At this level, Energy Agencies also incorporate basic smart technologies, such as smart meters and building automation features, but without yet implementing full-scale digitalisation.

4.6.2 Overview of Advanced Policy Options in participating MS across policy measures

EPC scope: For the advanced Policy Option, Energy Agencies identified the aim of expansion of assessment-based certification for similar buildings, planning to adopt this for certain building types, including single-family houses.

EPC triggers and methods: Measures of this pillar are implemented by only a few countries at the advanced level of Policy Options and reflect a transition towards a more comprehensive EPC framework. This includes ensuring EPC affordability and financial support for vulnerable households. At this level, some countries aim to integrate additional elements into EPC assessments and stricter methodologies for evaluating ventilation and indoor climate conditions.

EPC uptake and display: Advanced Policy Options focus on making EPC compliance easier. Energy Agencies aim to simplify procedures to update EPCs when minor upgrades are made, allowing for incremental improvements to be reflected without the need for full reassessment. Another key aspect of advanced level is the link between EPCs and renovation incentives. Policies require building owners of EPC-rated C and below to be invited to one-stop shops for

renovation advice. Similarly, sellers of buildings undergoing renovations before a sale are required to provide projections on future energy demand.

Experts and enforcement: Energy Agencies aim to improve control mechanisms and enforcement at the advanced level by implementing mandatory certification of EPC experts under specific legal frameworks, ensuring that those conducting assessments are formally recognised under established standards. There appears a stronger focus on educational campaigns and training programs. In terms of enforcement, quality checks on EPC assessments are commonly included.

EPC design and content: Energy Agencies aim to incorporate additional indicators to EPCs such as smart readiness assessment values, digital building logbook availability, and connections to district heating and cooling networks. These additions make EPCs more functional in urban energy planning and enable deeper integration into national energy efficiency strategies. EPCs at this level provide deeper insights into energy storage systems, electric vehicle charging infrastructure, and feasibility assessments for upgrading heating, cooling, and domestic hot water systems to more efficient settings. Recommendations become more actionable with some countries incorporating payback period estimates, cost-benefit analyses, and financial incentive information.

Databases: Energy Agencies include transformation of EPC databases into interconnected platforms at the advanced level, allowing data sharing across different registries and digital tools. Integration with digital building logbooks ensures that EPCs at this level are part of a broader digital ecosystem for managing building performance data. More Energy Agencies include the requirement to make aggregated and anonymous EPC data available for public use and allowing research institutions to request access.

Integration: Energy Agencies define that at the advanced Policy Option level EPCs are to begin to function as part of a broader digital ecosystem, integrating with energy management systems and smart technology infrastructures. Policies encourage the use of energy management systems, recognising real-time monitoring and optimisation of energy consumption as crucial for improving building efficiency. While AI and machine learning remain in the early stages of adoption, some countries aim to explore how these technologies can be used to enhance EPC functionality, including predictive analytics for energy efficiency improvements and automated recommendations for building renovations.

BRP: At the advanced level, policies focus on ensuring BRPs are issued digitally by experts after on-site inspections, making updates and adjustments easier. Expert involvement will become more structured, with mandatory discussions with renovation professionals after BRP issuance. At this level, BRPs also integrate with digital logbooks, allowing property owners and authorities to track renovation progress over time.

SRI implementation: Energy Agencies consider SRI measures to focus on enhancing system interoperability and integrating digital features such as digital twins, smart controls, and adaptive energy demand management. Agencies include the introduction of automated SRI assessment methods, making it easier to evaluate a building's smart readiness without extensive manual calculations. Other developments at this level include standardised web-based SRI assessment toolkits, allowing multiple stakeholders such as energy auditors, building managers, and policymakers to access and interpret SRI data efficiently.

4.6.3 Overview of Comprehensive Policy Options in participating MS across policy measures

EPC scope: The comprehensive level of adoption of measures in this pillar includes all additional requirements to the EPC certification which were not included in the baselines.

EPC triggers and methods: Energy Agencies include all additional methodologies and incorporate further accounting for passive solar protection, stricter ventilation assessment, and enhanced operational energy performance calculations. Measures ensuring EPC affordability and financial support for vulnerable households are also emphasised at this level.

EPC uptake and display: At the most ambitious level, Energy Agencies aim to implement fully digital EPC updates based on certified methods. Public awareness and engagement are prioritised. The role of EPCs as a driver for renovation is further shaped through measures requiring owners of buildings rated C and below to be systematically invited to one-stop shops for renovation guidance.

Experts and enforcement: Energy Agencies aim to implement comprehensive control and education measures to ensure the long-term credibility of EPCs. Educational campaigns and training programs ensure that both experts and the general public are well-informed about EPC regulations. Mandatory quality checks, regular validation, and the availability of EPC reports on request are implemented in the EPC framework.

EPC design and content: Energy Agencies aim to update EPC design and content to the maximum including all additional measures and requirements. EPCs transform into fully integrated digital tools that provide real-time, data-driven insights into a building's energy performance. EPCs at this level fully integrate with renovation support mechanisms, linking building owners to one-stop shops for renovation advice and providing digital renovation passports for tracking efficiency improvements over time. The recommendations section includes detailed assessments on all system settings, lifespan analyses of heating systems, and standardised conditions for energy savings assessments. EPCs at this level incorporate broader financial and policy integration, displaying potential revenues from energy efficiency schemes like White Certificates and including energy price forecasts to help owners make informed financial decisions.

Databases: EPC data management is to become a fully integrated, highly automated system. EPC databases become fully interoperable with digital building logbooks. Data protection is strengthened with advanced encryption and access control mechanisms, ensuring that sensitive information remains secure while still being accessible for policymaking and research.

Integration: Most Energy Agencies identified that EPCs must become fully integrated with advanced digital technologies at the comprehensive level, forming the smart, data-driven energy management systems. The adoption of smart building technologies and IoT devices is common, enabling real-time energy tracking, automated energy adjustments, and AI-driven insights for property owners and regulators.

BRP: At the comprehensive level of ambition, BRPs become automated digital renovation management tools, integrating AI-based insights, financial planning modules, and EPC data connectivity. Policies focus on developing dedicated digital tools for BRP preparation, updates, and real-time modifications after renovations are completed. The storage of BRPs in digital logbooks is required, ensuring long-term documentation and compliance tracking.

Experts are required to use EPC data to describe a building's status, creating a seamless link between energy performance assessments and renovation planning.

SRI implementation: Energy Agencies aim to make SRI fully automated and integrated into smart building management systems, using AI and machine learning to optimise energy efficiency in real-time. An emphasis is given to training and capacity building, with the development of certification programs, multilingual e-learning platforms, and ethical guidelines for SRI assessors.

4.7 Theory of Change

The theory of change describes how the combination of measures in each policy option contributes to the desired actions and thereby induces the impact both tackling the drivers of the problem and thereby contributing to the achievement of specific and general objectives.

Methodology

The theory of change is based on most recent available research in how policy can change the behaviour of stakeholders with regard to building performance, in particular energy efficiency and renewable energy measures. The theory was co-developed by all partners with research input provided by the TST.

The below described theory of change is utilised by all energy agencies in their national reports and customised should the focus vary, or national conditions or evidence indicate different priorities. However, the differences are expected are small in nature.

Overview of the theory of change

The following **factors** are being influenced by the policy option described above to achieve the specific objectives identified to resolve the causes identified in the problem tree:

- **Access to information, awareness and understanding:** making EPC data accessible and available for both individual users and multipliers
- **Accuracy of EPC:** improving transparency and accuracy of EPC data
- **Trust in EPC by individual building owners and multipliers:** enhancing reliability of the EPC process and data
- **Efficiency (business and authorities):** efficiency of administrative support and policymaking in energy efficiency sphere
- **Integration of SRI:** implementation of SRI and integration with other systems and tools.

In combination these factors increase the **ability and willingness to act**.

Increased ability and willingness to act makes the following **desired actions** more likely. Thus, the factors influence the behaviour of stakeholders, individual building owners, and multipliers (eligible parties such as financial institutions, aggregators, energy suppliers, energy services providers):

- **Deeper renovation:** building owners and multipliers are motivated for processing deep renovations
- **Additional renovation:** building owners and multipliers are persuaded in effectiveness of additional renovations
- **Renewable Energy Sources and Storage:** ensured higher rate of RES installation and usage

Through an uptake of the desired actions, impacts are generated thereby aiding to achieve the general objectives for the policy initiative Impacts:

- **Environmental impact:** reduction of GHG emissions and other negative environmental impacts
- **Economic impact:** reduction of energy costs, attraction of investments in the sector, cost-effective policy implementation, and economic growth
- **Social impact:** reduction of energy poverty level and creation of new jobs

The theory of change is summarised in the following graphic:

4.8 Contributing factors

4.8.1 Access to information, awareness and understanding

Policy measures improving access to information about building performance a) increases the quantity and quality of data property owners and multipliers (i.e. developers, experts and policymakers) can process, also b) reducing operational costs including administrative burden.

Energetic decisions are expensive and thus require sufficient evidence to be considered. User-friendly presentation on the EPC makes it more likely that the information is recognised and processed. Provision in digital formats permits to share more information than on paper alone. Indeed, the enhanced EPC should not be seen as a traditional paper-based document but rather as a digital information resource. The next-generation energy performance certification will meet several key requirements: (i) improved data quality, (ii) enriched and integrated data—including the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), sustainability indicators, and real energy consumption metrics, and (iii) a dynamic and flexible structure, allowing updates throughout a building's lifecycle and customization for different purposes and user groups.¹ Digital formats can be more readily shared simplifying the process of gathering answers or seeking advice. These aspects achieve awareness of the current building performance and initial understanding of the potentials of future performance.²

Follow-up activities including deeper analysis (BRP) or human interaction (expert consultation, one-stop-shops) provide further information, increase awareness and deeper understanding.

Costs are lowered through single-point of access, reliable and time-independent access to information by, for instance, reducing the amount of time searching for piece of information. Multipliers are enabled to perform targeted search and analysis uncovering systemically missed opportunities, inefficiencies of procedures. Findings can be used to instruct experts and staff at one-stop-shops hereby also streamlining utilisation of funding at reduced administrative burden.

The costs of integrating and utilising data can be lowered through interoperable systems ensure that EPC data is harmonised and easily integrated into market transactions. The integration of auxiliary data, such as actual energy use and GIS data, extends the applicability

¹ Zuljan, V., Mikulčić, H., Palombo, A., & Seljak, T. (2025). Novel technologies for the sustainable development of energy, water and environmental systems. Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments, 104192.

² D2.3 Report on users' perception on EPC scheme in U-CERT partner countries

of EPCs through merge of data and enhances their validation providing independent estimates for reported values making EPCs a more reliable tool for policy enforcement and market efficiency.³

Access to regularly updated information based on near-time measurements increases the quality of information of building performance as well as making it more reliable to the recipient of information (i.e. closing the distance of cause and effect) which makes awareness and thereby understanding more likely.⁴

Improving accessibility and interoperability of EPCs, building owners and multipliers are enabled to make better-informed energy decisions, reduce costs, and thereby enhance the effectiveness of any linked energy policy.

4.8.2 Accuracy of EPC

EPC data accurately reflecting the true energy performance of buildings ensures that effective measures are taken leading to the desired outcome.

Improved accuracy in EPC methodologies improves the identification of energy-saving opportunities. Reliable EPC data helps multipliers and individual building owners make informed decisions about approach to energy performance of a building, ensuring that energy-saving measures are effectively implemented, monitored, and optimised.

Frequent EPC renewals and integration of BRP guarantees higher data quality as it provides a comprehensive overview of building performance, ensuring that outdated information does not influence the decisions on taking actions for energy efficiency.⁵ Up-to-date EPCs encourage property owners and tenants to take timely action, fostering contribution to continuous energy performance improvements. Recommendations for renovations based on the reliable EPC data enables long-term renovation planning.^{6 7}

Additionally, accurate EPCs provided by certified experts enhance energy performance monitoring, ensuring that renovations achieve their intended goals. This leads to more effective retrofits, lower energy consumption, reduced reliance on fossil fuels, and significant GHG reductions.

Improving accuracy of EPC data play a direct role in supporting sustainable decision-making of individual building owners and multipliers, aligning the building sector with climate objectives and driving renovations.

4.8.3 Trust in EPC by individual building owners and multipliers

Transparency in EPC data and processes is essential for public confidence. Current EPCs are not widely regarded as a benchmark for quality housing, as buyers and tenants do not consider

³ Tsatsakis, K., Tsitsanis, A., Malavazos, C., 2017. Enhanced human-centric building energy performance rating: Operational rating and behavioral change in the scope of OrbEEt project, In: Presented at the 2017 Global Internet of Things Summit, IEEE, Geneva, Switzerland, pp. 1–6. doi:10.1109/GIOTS.2017.8016268.

⁴ <https://time.com/7201501/ai-buildings-energy-efficiency/>

⁵ iBRoad2EPC-D2.2-Conceptualising-iBRoad2EPC-2023-02-BPIE.pdf

⁶ Long Term Renovation Strategy - SECCA

⁷ Backhaus J, Tigchelaar C, De Best-Waldhober M. Key findings & policy recommendations to improve effectiveness of Energy Performance Certificates & the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive vol. 47. 2011 accessed <https://www.ecn.nl/docs/library/report/2011/o11083.pdf>, Accessed date: 19 December 2018.

them as a key factor in property decisions.⁸ The inclusion of concrete recommendations increases the perceived usefulness of the EPC.⁹

Publicly available EPC data supports research and policymaking, ensuring that energy efficiency measures align with climate goals.¹⁰ Frequent EPC updates and shorter validity periods keep performance data up to date, encouraging timely energy-efficient upgrades.

Improved EPC methodologies enhance trust and market transparency, making sustainable investments more attractive. When data is accurate and accessible, property owners and financial institutions are more likely to invest in renovations aimed at energy efficiency. Clear and transparent EPC layouts including nZEB and ZEB benchmarks¹¹ guide sustainable upgrades and increase awareness in the real estate market.¹² Moreover, inaccurate energy certificates affect the economic valuation of buildings by assigning incorrect energy performance labels. Since higher energy efficiency is linked to a “premium price,” mislabelling can distort market assessments.^{13,14}

Trust in EPCs plays a key role in reducing energy poverty, particularly when low-performing buildings receive targeted support. Free access to EPC data ensures a fair and transparent housing market, empowering tenants and buyers to make energy-conscious choices. Robust data security measures strengthen public confidence in the EPC system.

Trust, reliability, awareness, and knowledge significantly shape how people perceive existing EPCs. Many property owners hesitate to invest in energy efficiency improvements due to various factors, including resistance to change, financial concerns, limited knowledge or interest, and a lack of understanding of the benefits and opportunities. Distrust toward stakeholders involved in the certification process further discourages action, preventing wider adoption of energy-efficient upgrades.¹⁵

Improvements in transparency and trust to EPC processes supports a fair housing market, reduces energy poverty, and encourages energy-efficient investments.

4.8.4 Efficiency (business and authorities)

Various factors regarding EPC process increase efficiency of administrative support to building owners. Efficient EPC systems lower administrative and compliance costs for building owners, developers, and policymakers. Interoperable systems between EPC, BRP, and SRI facilitate smoother transactions and renovations, while digital formats enable smart energy management and retrofit planning. A transparent EPC system also strengthens market confidence, ensuring that energy performance becomes a key factor in property valuation. Furthermore, the quality of energy certificates is influenced by market regulations in each

⁸ D2.3 Report on users' perception on EPC scheme in U-CERT partner countries p.6

⁹ Backhaus J, Tigchelaar C, De Best-Waldhober M. Key findings & policy recommendations to improve effectiveness of Energy Performance Certificates & the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive vol. 47. 2011 accessed <https://www.ecn.nl/docs/library/report/2011/o11083.pdf>, Accessed date: 19 December 2018.

¹⁰ Public Access to Building Related Energy Data for Better Decision Making in Implementing Energy Efficiency Strategies: Legal Barriers and Technical Challenges

¹¹ Nearly-zero energy and zero-emission buildings - European Commission

¹² Energy Performance Certificates: boosting the market for energy efficient buildings | BUILD UP

¹³ Khazal A, Sønstebo OJ. Valuation of energy performance certificates in the rental market – professionals vs. nonprofessionals. Energy Policy 2020;147:111830.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111830>.

¹⁴ Hårsman B, Daghbashyan Z, Chaudhary P. On the quality and impact of residential energy performance certificates. Energy Buildings 2016;133:711–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2016.10.033>.

¹⁵ D2.3 Report on users' perception on EPC scheme in U-CERT partner countries p.7

Member State, where the cost of an EPC often does not correspond to its actual value. In this context, adopting regulated pricing mechanisms may be more effective than standardized tariffs, which do not account for factors such as building complexity, data collection efforts, or energy model development. From this perspective, Arcipowska et al. analysed EPC price variations for single-family homes across EU countries, revealing significant discrepancies and the market's inability to establish a stable pricing structure.¹⁶

Transparent and regularly updated EPC data allows buyers and tenants to make better financial decisions, encouraging investments in energy-efficient buildings. A unified EPC identity and integration of operational and embodied emissions data support a lifecycle approach to sustainability, helping stakeholders consider both short- and long-term environmental impacts. At the same time authorities receive better tools to track energy efficiency progress which help to enforce regulations. Comprehensive databases and integration with policy tools allow authorities and businesses to develop targeted sustainable policies. Data-driven decision-making lowers policy development costs, supporting effective regulations that promote energy efficiency.¹⁷ Affordability measures and financial support ensure that EPC benefits reach all layers of society, reducing energy poverty while long-term energy savings offset administrative costs.

Efficient and transparent EPC systems reduce administrative burdens, enhance market confidence, support data-driven policymaking, and promote energy-efficient investments, increasing ability to support more building owners at same costs.

4.8.5 Integration of SRI

Integrating SRI functionalities with other energy management systems makes buildings more adaptive, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly thus more attractive to real estate market. In the study conducted by Apostolopoulos et al.¹⁸ is demonstrated how the level of smartness of residential buildings constructed after the implementation of the EPBD in Europe can be increased with a relatively low cost. The increased adoption of SRI improves energy efficiency, enhances grid responsiveness, and reduces energy waste and GHG emissions. Advanced technologies, such as real-time monitoring and automated energy-saving solutions, optimise energy management^{19,20}. For example, Markoska et al.²¹ attempted to identify the minimum SRI value required to automate the assessment of building energy performance, using the Performance Testing (PTing) framework applied to a university building in Denmark. Flexible energy demand and interoperability improve grid stability, supporting a transition to cleaner energy systems.

The implementation of SRI in non-residential buildings promotes energy optimisation, significantly reducing energy consumption and emissions. The integration of EPC, BRP, and SRI

¹⁶ Arcipowska A, Anagnostopoulos F, Mariottini F, Kunkel S. Energy performance certificates across the EU. Buildings Performance Institute Europe (BPIE) 2015: 46–7.

¹⁷ JRC Technical Report - Harmonisation of datasets of Energy.

¹⁸ V. Apostolopoulos, P. Giourka, G. Martinopoulos, K. Angelakoglou, K. Kourtzanidis, N. Nikolopoulos, Smart readiness indicator evaluation and cost estimation of smart retrofitting scenarios - A comparative case-study in European residential buildings, *Sustain Cities Soc* 82 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2022.103921>.

¹⁹ S. Athanasaki, K. Tsikaloudaki, Smart buildings for smart cities: Analysis of the Smart Readiness Indicator, *Green Energy and Sustainability* (2022). <https://doi.org/10.47248/ges2202020005>.

²⁰ O. Adegov, S. Shekhorkina, M. Babenko, M. Lyahovetska-Tokareva, O. Kudryavcev, Smart-Readiness Assessment of a Complex Residential Building in Ukraine, *Slovak Journal of Civil Engineering* 30 (2022) 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.2478/sjce-2022-0009>.

²¹ E. Markoska, N. Jakica, S. Lazarova-Molnar, M.K. Kragh, Assessment of Building Intelligence Requirements for Real Time Performance Testing in Smart Buildings, 2019 4th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies, *SpliTech 2019* (2019). <https://doi.org/10.23919/SpliTech.2019.8783002>.

systems enhances data accuracy and transparency, reducing administrative costs and enabling targeted energy efficiency measures to be planned and taken.

By providing decision support tools and clear recommendations, SRI enables informed investment decisions and long-term cost savings by reducing energy waste and lower operational expenses.

Integrating SRI with energy management systems enhances efficiency, reduces emissions, lowers costs, and increases real estate market attractiveness while supporting a transition to cleaner energy systems.

4.9 Desired actions

The combination of above listed factors **increases the ability and willingness of building owners and multipliers to act**. The following sections describe the impacts achieved.

4.9.1 Deeper renovation

Building owners benefitting from better information in their EPC as well as provided by BRP recommendations and SRI system are enabled to be aware and comprehend which measures aimed at improving energy efficiency are possible for their building. The additional information is more likely to be trusted, and any additional support is more likely to be provided. When individual building owners are enabled to act, understand the environmental, financial, and social benefits, and are informed about their property's energy efficiency and potential improvements, they become more likely to act leading to renovations achieving higher energy efficiency and thereby higher energy savings.

The extent of this impact is deemed to grow with the complexity and completeness of the measures provided.

The accuracy of EPCs encourages stakeholders to commit to deeper renovations by providing reliable data that ensures the most impactful energy-saving measures are identified. Trust in EPCs reinforces this behaviour, reducing hesitation among building owners and developers. When EPC methodologies are transparent, stakeholders perceive deep renovation investments as credible and worthwhile.²²

Digital and user-friendly platforms and databases increase building owners' engagement by providing clear and actionable recommendations, ensuring that energy-efficient measures are incorporated into deep renovation projects.

Additionally, streamlined processes between EPC, BRP, and SRI ensure efficient project execution, removing administrative bottlenecks that might otherwise constrain or postpone deep renovations. Accessible step-by-step guides and recommendations support broader engagement. Building owners are more inclined to proceed deep renovations when they are provided with a roadmap from BRP and see digital upgrade potential showed by SRI. Providing contact information for one-stop shops simplifies the process of accessing assistance and increases trust in the system.

4.9.2 Additional renovation

The availability of EPC data and supportive infrastructure promotes additional renovation activities by simplifying decision-making and reducing uncertainty. Those building owners who

²² QualDeEPC - Harnessing energy performance certificates for deep energy renovation: Policy recommendations and evidence from testing

undertake minor improvements are more likely to consider additional renovations if they have access to transparent data about energy performance and available financial incentives.

Higher accuracy of EPC data provides a foundation for additional upgrades by ensuring that the reported energy savings are reliable. Trust in EPCs encourages building owners to reinvest in energy efficiency improvements, knowing that their investments will bring certain benefits. By integrating EPCs with BRP and SRI, stakeholders can efficiently plan phased renovations which align with sustainability goals, allowing for systematic enhancements to building performance over time.

Efficiency in EPC processes and financial support mechanisms enable authorities and businesses to promote staggered renovation efforts. Building owners are encouraged to continue upgrading their properties beyond the initial renovation phase when administrative burdens are minimised, and financial incentives are more accessible.

4.9.3 Renewable Energy Sources and Storage

Upgraded EPC and SRI system encourage the use of RES such as solar panels, heat pumps, and battery storage. The integration of RES and storage solutions is significantly influenced by EPC accessibility, trust, and efficiency. When building owners and multipliers have reliable EPC data and clear understanding of current and potential building energy performance, they can better assess the feasibility and benefits of integrating RES.

Accurate EPC data provides essential information for optimising the use of RES. Trust in EPC methodologies strengthens the confidence in the effectiveness of RES solutions, reducing distrust about long-term energy savings.

RES adoption is also facilitated with digital platforms and interoperable systems which improve the integration of EPCs with renewable energy incentive programs, helping building owners find ways to manage financial and administrative complexities. SRI functionalities enable intelligent energy management, optimising the performance of RES and storage systems, thereby increasing energy efficiency gains and leading to lower carbon footprints.

4.10 Impacts

Impacts describe the desired outcomes stated or implied in general objectives. The following describes three key impact areas as defined by the BRG.

4.10.1 Environmental impact

Increased EPC coverage and its integration with other systems and tools ensures better energy performance data, which increases the possibility and willingness for retrofits and thus reducing GHG emissions and other negative environmental impacts.

When EPCs are widely accessible, property owners and policymakers can implement energy-saving measures that significantly reduce GHG emissions and lower the overall environmental footprint of buildings. Accurate EPCs enable more precise energy performance monitoring, ensuring that renovations achieve their intended sustainability goals. Trust in EPC systems increases stakeholder engagement in energy efficiency projects, fostering continuous improvement in building performance.

Efficient EPC frameworks help authorities design targeted policies that support carbon footprint reduction initiatives and transition to sustainable urban development. The integration of SRI with EPC and BRP systems emphasise environmental benefits by optimising energy use and reducing energy waste. By facilitating smart grid interactions, SRI improves energy

distribution and consumption patterns, supporting the broader transition toward carbon neutrality.

Overall, improving access to EPC data, enhancing its accuracy, and increasing building owners' and managers' trust contribute to more ambitious renovation projects, higher adoption of renewable energy sources, and significant environmental benefits through reduced emissions and increased energy efficiency.

4.10.2 Economic impact

The implementation of energy efficiency measures driven by accurate and accessible EPC data brings economic benefits for individual building owners, industry and construction sector as well as country.

By improving energy performance, property values increase, making energy-efficient buildings more attractive to buyers and investors. Additional integration of smart technologies and energy management systems optimise consumption, lowering operational costs and preventing resource waste. Reduced energy costs achieved by transparent EPC layouts enable informed energy decisions and lead to financial savings for building owners, tenants, and businesses, creating long-term economic stability.

Simplified certification methods lower compliance costs for stakeholders, while improved market transparency and regular EPC updates support energy-efficient investments. They in turn stimulate creation of new jobs in multiple sectors, including construction, manufacturing, and technology. The demand for skilled labour in energy auditing, retrofitting, and smart energy management grows, contributing to economic growth. Additionally, financial incentives and support programs encourage private-sector investment, further driving economic activity and innovation in sustainable building programs.

Efficiency in EPC processes reduces administrative costs for building owners, developers, and multipliers, allowing bigger support in energy-efficient renovations. Access to energy data for local authorities and researchers supports data-driven policies, reducing costs for policy development and implementation. Governments and policymakers benefit from cost-effective policy implementation, ensuring that funding allocated for energy efficiency programs are used efficiently to maximise impact.

4.10.3 Social impact

Enhanced EPCs contribute to various social benefits by improving housing conditions, reducing energy poverty, and increasing public awareness of energy efficiency. When EPCs provide clear and reliable energy performance data, it enables tenants and building owners to make better-informed decisions, leading to improved living conditions and lower energy costs. Open access to EPC data fosters a fair housing market as it enables vulnerable households to access financial support for energy efficiency improvements.

Improved trust to EPC data and processes strengthens public engagement in energy-saving measures, encouraging wider adoption of sustainable practices. Additionally, the increase of use and understanding of EPCs boost construction sector as the demand for energy-efficient materials, skilled experts and energy consultants grow. Energy efficiency initiatives create new job opportunities for experts in the construction, energy, and technology sectors, promoting economic growth and workforce development.

5 Conclusion

The development of Policy Options carried out within tunES demonstrate that a structured methodology based on the EU Better Regulation Guidelines provides a strong foundation for policy design and enables Member States to design coherent, ambitious, and feasible policy options for improving EPC and SRI schemes. By combining shared analytical tools such as Problem and Objective Trees, baseline scenario, etc, with national flexibility, the project has produced a robust and replicable framework that strengthens policy coherence, supports effective EPBD implementation, and lays the ground for measurable environmental, economic, and social impacts in the buildings sector.

Across the seven participating Member States, an average of 33% of measures were already implemented in the baseline, while the preferred Policy Options are expected to introduce an additional 58% of measures, resulting in an overall expected coverage of 91% of all identified measures. This high level of coverage demonstrates that the BRG-based approach not only supports structured policy design but also makes an ambitious and comprehensive alignment with EPBD requirements more likely which goes beyond minimum transposition and addressing a wide range of regulatory, technical, and implementation gaps.

The tunES framework was offered as a replicable and directly deployable tool to all Member States currently conducting their transpositions efforts. Going beyond the main purpose, the tool could be useful in future EPBD evaluations and transposition comparisons in being able to record planned and actual transposition, help identify gaps, and facilitate cross-country benchmarking. In this way, tunES contributes not only to improved national policy development but also to enhanced monitoring, comparability, and learning at EU level, supporting more effective implementation of building energy policies.

ANNEX 1. tunES Policy Measures and Policy Options

This Annex is attached in the separate excel file named:

tunES D3.3 Report on Ex-ante Testing and Policy Options - Annex 1 - tunES Policy Measures and Policy Options.

The file contains the full list of Policy Measures and collection of Policy Options and Baselines identified by Energy Agencies